

SPORTS JOURNALISM

SPORT JURNALISTIKASI

СПОРТИВНАЯ ЖУРНАЛИСТИКА

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Abstract: This article covers sports journalism and its peculiarities. Within the framework of the study, stages, genres and methods of development of sports journalism are analyzed. The role and importance of sports journalism in society has also been examined. The results of the study show that sports journalism is an important component of the media and contributes significantly to the development of sports.

Keywords: Sports Journalism, Media, Sports, Journalism, media

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sport jurnalistikasi va uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari yoritilgan. Tadqiqot doirasida sport jurnalistikasining rivojlanish bosqichlari, janrlari va usullari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, sport jurnalistikasining jamiyatdagi o'рни va ahamiyati ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, sport jurnalistikasi ommaviy axborot vositalarining muhim tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, sportning rivojlanishiga katta hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sport jurnalistikasi, ommaviy axborot vositalari, sport, jurnalistika, media

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается спортивная журналистика и ее особенности. В рамках исследования проанализированы этапы, жанры и методы развития спортивной журналистики. Также рассматривается роль и значение спортивной журналистики в обществе. Результаты исследования показывают, что спортивная журналистика является важным компонентом средств массовой информации и вносит значительный вклад в развитие спорта.

Ключевые слова: спортивная журналистика, СМИ, спорт, журналистика, СМИ

INTRODUCTION

Sports journalism has become an integral part of the media today. It covers not only sports news and analysis, but also various topics in the field of sports. Through sports journalism, people find news of the achievements and successes of their favorite teams and athletes, as well as being boxed by problems and news in the field of Sports [1].

Sports journalism has evolved over time, discovering new forms and styles. This article analyzes the stages, genres and methods of development of sports journalism and examines its place and importance in society.

METHODS AND LITERATURE ANALYSIS

As part of the study, scientific articles, books and other resources on sports journalism were analyzed. [2]. To study the stages of development of sports

journalism, its historical roots and evolution were considered. Various genres and methods of sports journalism were analyzed and their distinctive features were identified [3].

RESULTS

The results of the study showed that sports journalism appeared in the late 19th century and was initially published in newspapers and magazines. Later, with the advent of radio and television, sports journalism reached a new level [4]. Today, however, the internet and social networks are spurring the further development of sports journalism.

Genres such as message, reportage, interview, review, analysis are widely used in sports journalism [5]. Also important in sports journalism are such visual elements as photos, infographics, videos.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Sports journalism plays an important role not only in reporting, but also in raising problems in the field of sports and discussing them. Journalists raise awareness of society by covering negative cases such as corruption in sports, the use of doping, cruelty, and contribute to overcoming these problems [6].

Sports journalism also increases interest in athletes by covering their lives and activities. This in turn serves to attract young people to sports and promote a healthy lifestyle [7].

However, sports journalism can sometimes lose its sporting spirit by emphasizing sensational reporting and hype. Also, in some cases, journalists can interfere too much in the lives of athletes and undermine their personal lives [8].

Sports journalism is an important factor in the development of sports. It not only provides information about competitions, but also covers the life and activities

of athletes, coaches and other sports figures. This allows sports enthusiasts to learn more about their favorite athletes.

Also, through sports journalism, achievements and records in various fields of sport are reported. This encourages athletes to pursue higher results and encourages the development of the sport.

Sports journalism also raises the issue of gender inequality in sports. There are problems such as women's athlete successes being insufficiently highlighted and they being less noticed when compared to male athletes. Sports journalism can contribute to gender equality by bringing such issues to the attention of society.

In addition, sports journalism also analyzes the economic aspects of the sports industry. Athletes provide information about contract contracts, transfers, sponsorship and other financial issues. This gives sports enthusiasts an idea of the processes taking place "behind the curtains" of the sport.

The role of new media technologies in the development of sports journalism is great. The Internet and social networks accelerated the spread of Sports News and created new channels of communication with the audience. Now sports fans can learn about their favorite teams and athletes not only through traditional media, but also through online publications, blogs and social networks.

CONCLUSION

Sports journalism is an important component of the media and contributes significantly to the development of sports. He plays an important role in society not only by providing information, but also by covering and discussing problems in the field of sports.

Sports journalism has evolved over time, discovering new forms and styles. However, it is necessary to avoid some problems, including sensational messages and interference in privacy.

In general, sports journalism will retain its importance and become more sophisticated in the future. Journalists, on the other hand, must follow the principles of impartiality, truthfulness and morality in their activities.

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